

**GULF MIGRATION, REMITTANCES AND PROGRESS: THE
EXPERIENCE FROM NORTH INDIA**

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Abstract:

Gulf migration refers to the large-scale movement of workers, primarily from South Asian countries to the oil-rich states of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC). Following the discovery of oil in the 1970s, it was fuelled by the rapid economic growth of the region. It created a massive demand for labour in sectors such as construction, services and domestic work. According to S. Irudaya Rajan, Gulf migration from countries like India has been primarily driven by economic factors, with workers seeking better wages and living conditions than those available in their home countries (Rajan, 2014, p.12). He highlights that Gulf migration, especially from rural areas of India is often motivated by the need to escape poverty, unemployment and underemployment in agriculture-dependent economies. Devesh Kapur also argues that this migration is shaped by the structural mismatch between the labour-surplus economies of South Asia and the labour-deficient but capital-rich economies of the Gulf (Kapur, 2016, p.103). This mismatch creates a “push-pull” dynamic where Gulf countries pull in workers due to labour shortages, while South Asian countries push workers abroad due to limited local employment opportunities.

This research paper seeks to explore the underlying processes, key determinants, and far-reaching consequences of Gulf migration from this region. Framed within the broader agenda of the Sustainable

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Development Goals (SDGs), the study aims to investigate how this migration pattern affects both the migrants and their communities back home. The methodology of the research paper is based on empirical field surveys in rural North India where primary data is collected under a mixed method approach of study design. Findings of the primary data show an interconnection between internal and international migration where internal migration leads to international migration under the push and pull factor of migration. From these perspectives, the impact of Gulf migration improved the socio-economic status of migrant households and led to a demonstration of its impact. Apart, the entire function of Gulf migration enhanced the sustainable development goals (SDGs) of the United Nations. Consequently, it would motivate researchers, politicians, and academics to pursue deeper investigation in the field of migration studies.

Keyword: migration, remittances, gulf cooperation council, sustainable development goals

1. Introduction

Gulf migration from India has become a significant socio-economic trend since the 1970s. It was driven by the demand for labour in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) states. India is the largest contributor to this migration, with over 9.3 million migrants in the region is largely from states like Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, and Rajasthan. The trend shows that majority are from the rural regions. And, migration from rural North India is influenced by wage disparities, unemployment, and strong social networks that facilitate movement to the Gulf. While remittances have significantly improved household incomes, education and living standards but also challenges such as worker exploitation and family separation persist (elaborated further in the study).

India is the predominant supplier of migrants in GCC nations owing to the substantial need for laborers in these regions. Indian are the biggest among migrants for GCC states, with a total of 9.3 million, constituting 31.08 percent of the overall migrant population in the GCC countries (Table 1).

Table 1: Trend Wise Analysis of Total Stock of Indian Migrants in GCC states

Origin Countries	1990		2000		2010		2019	
	Number	Total %	Number	Total %	Number	Total %	Number	Total %
Afghanistan	169818	2.1	179601	1.8	290985	1.5	482513	1.6
Bangladesh	868071	10.6	1102772	11.0	2345627	11.8	3346430	11.1
India	1955742	23.9	2739058	27.2	6441256	32.3	9326699	31.08
Nepal	181494	2.2	191943	1.9	392998	2.0	800779	2.6
Pakistan	902311	11.0	1128309	11.2	2306422	11.6	3314910	11.04
Sri Lanka	302154	3.7	293588	2.9	517340	2.6	868821	2.8
Sub Total of South Asian in GCC States	4379590	53.6	5635271	56.0	12294628	61.7	18140152	60.4
Sub Total of Rest of World in GCC States	3786785	46.4	4425097	44.0	7618208	38.3	11861362	39.6
Total	8166375	100.0	100,60,368	100.0	19912836	100.0	30001514	100.0

Source: Compiled and Analyzed by Author from United Nation Migrant Stock by Origin and Destination, 1990-2019

The proportion of Indian migrants is leading in GCC states where Indian migrants accounted for 58.0 per cent of the total stock of migrants in Oman followed by 43.0 per cent in Bahrain, 39.8 per cent in UAE, 37.0 per cent in Kuwait, 31.3 per cent in Kuwait and 18.6 per cent in Saudi Arabia. Nationalization policies of Saudi Arabia declined the trend of Indian migrants with the rest of the South Asian migrants (Table 2).

Table 1.2: Country Wise Analysis of South Asian Migrants in GCC States (In Per Cent of Total Number of Migrants)

Origin Countries	Bahrain	Kuwait	Oman	Qatar	Saudi Arabia	UAE
India	43.0	37.0	58.0	31.3	18.6	39.8
Pakistan	10.6	10.9	10.5	10.6	11.0	11.4
Bangladesh	11.1	12.2	13.3	11.8	9.5	12.6
Combined Total of Above three	64.7	60.2	81.9	53.7	39.1	63.8

Total Per Cent of Rest of World	35.3	39.8	18.1	46.3	60.9	36.2
Total Numbers of Migrants	741161	3034845	2286226	2229688	13122338	8587256

Source: Compiled and Analysed by Author from United Nation Migrant Stock by Origin and Destination, 1990-2019

Inflow of Remittances from GCC States to India

GCC states are major remittances-sending countries to India due to the huge stock of Indian migrants in GCC states. In 2021, India received 89375 million US \$ as remittances from world countries, among them a proportion of GCC states was 58.0 per cent. Therefore, it can be analyzed that GCC states are major remittances sending countries for Indian remittances building (Table 3).

Table 3: Inflow of Remittances in India in 2021

Sending Countries	Remittances in Million US\$	Per cent of Total
Saudi Arabia	13052	14.6
Oman	6413	7.1
Bahrain	1833	2.0
UAE	19821	22.1
Kuwait	6356	7.1
Qatar	4432	4.9
Subtotal from GCC States	51907	58.0
Rest of World	37468	42.0
Total	89375	100.0

Source: Compiled by author from World Bank remittances matrix data 2021. Accessed from: www.worldbank.org

According to Rajan et al. (2017), North Indian states namely- Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Rajasthan received huge remittances from GCC states due to the huge stock of North Indian migrants in GCC states (Table 4).

Table 4: Stock of Remittances in Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Rajasthan

Remittances receiving States	Remittances in Crores (INR)
Uttar Pradesh	92104
Bihar	41429
Rajasthan	31421

Rajan et al. (2017)

2. Process and Impact of Gulf Migration in North India

The state of Kerala was the driving force behind the early phase of migration from India to Gulf nations. However, the most recent phenomenon of labor migration from India to Gulf countries is being driven by the states of North India, particularly Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. As stated by the Ministry of External Affairs of the government of India in 2014 2015, this event took place as a direct result of the globalization and rapid production. The salary gap drives the migratory mechanism from North India to GCC countries. Furthermore, a well-established channel for North Indian migrant workers traveling from rural North India to the Gulf underscores the significance of the social network system of migration (Sasikumar & Timothy, 2015). For example, the migration from rural North India to Gulf countries is primarily driven by internal migration. Study says that Indian Laborers initially relocate to Mumbai for employment before subsequently moving to the Gulf in search of superior job opportunities and higher wages compared to the low wages in Mumbai or Delhi (Majumder & Taukeer, 2019, pp. 162-174).

North Indian migrant labourers are engaged as unskilled and semi-skilled migrant labourers in the bottom segmentation of the labour market due to the huge demand for Indian migrant labourers in Gulf countries (Khadria, 2006). GCC states are major remittances sending countries due to huge numbers of unskilled and semi-skilled migrant labourers that work as temporary migrant labourers in the bottom segmentation of the labour market in Gulf countries (Naufal & Ali, 2010). Huge stock of Indian migrant labourers ensured the huge inflow of remittances from Gulf countries to Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Rajasthan (Rajan et al., 2017, pp. 85-94).

Migration is an important part of development because both factors lead to each other where migration increases the level of development and the consequence of development ensures the pathway of migration (Haas, 2010, pp. 227-264). There is a significant role of the Gulf migration in overall progress of migrants' labourers because they send both economic and social remittances from Gulf countries to rural Uttar Pradesh. These consequences enhanced the micro-based economy of migrant households as well as ensured the pathway of demonstration impact of Gulf migration (Taukeer, 2020, pp.123-138). There is a significant impact of the Gulf migration in rural Bihar because Gulf migration positively changed the socio-economic and cultural development of migrant households as well as enhanced the cultural route of migration from Bihar to Gulf countries (Rahman, 2001, pp.14). Rajasthan is the leading state in receiving remittances from Gulf countries due to the huge tendency of Gulf migration from rural Rajasthan (Rajan, 2004, pp. 497-509).

The impact of COVID-19 largely affected the internal and international migrant labourers in Rural North India because these migrant labourers lost their jobs and faced hurdle conditions due to return migration (Majumder, 2022). In the case of Kerala, return migrant labourers found themselves in very precarious conditions due to the large impact of COVID-19 and the continuous lockdown (Ansari & Rahman, 2001).

3. Methodology

Based on the above concise introduction and review of literature, it can be conceptualized that Gulf migration is positively associated with the function of the push and pull factor of migration in the context of the culture of migration from North India to Gulf countries. In these consequences, North Indian states receive huge remittances from Gulf countries and the inflow of remittances is creating the formation of building capacity of remittances. A consequence of building the capacity of remittances is also creating structural transformation in migrant households because migrant households invest remittances in productive and unproductive items. These consequences promote the demonstration impact of Gulf migration through the positive role of migration in development. Therefore, the major argument of this research paper is based on fill the gap of literature in the study area of Gulf migration regarding to enhance the research domain on global level. The objective

of this research paper is based find out the process, determinants and consequences impact of Gulf migration.

Sampling

It used multistage sampling in purposively selected North Indian states namely- Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and Rajasthan where Kushinagar and Maharajganj districts were selected purposively in Uttar Pradesh, Siwan and Gopalganj district in Bihar; Churu and Jhunjhunu districts were selected purposively in Rajasthan (Table 5). These selected districts were listed in 100 districts of India for labour migration from India to Gulf countries in 2023 (source: www.emigrate.gov.in). In each district, it was selected 250 return migrant households through stratified random sampling and return migrant labourers were selected as respondents through stratified random sampling technique. Therefore, it was selected a total of 1500 return migrant households in North India through conducting field visits in 2023. Apart from that, Lucknow district was also covered in a study where 180 return migrant households were stratified and randomly selected through field visits from December 2017 to March 2018.

Table 5: Trends of Labour Migration from Top Five Indian States to Gulf Countries

Year	Total Emigration Clearances of Migrant Labourers	1 st rank	2 nd rank	3 rd rank	4 th rank	5 th rank
		States	States	States	States	States
2019	353126	U.P. (31.9)	Bihar (15.09)	Rajasthan (8.1)	West Bengal (7.2)	Tamil Nadu (7.01)
2020	90602	U.P. (31.1)	Bihar (14.6)	Kerala (9.3)	West Bengal (7.2)	Tamil Nadu (6.43)
2021	129442	U.P (25.9)	Bihar (18.1)	Rajasthan (8.7)	Kerala (8.0)	West Bengal (7.5)
2022	356383	U.P (33.7)	Bihar (16.3)	Rajasthan (8.0)	West Bengal (7.7)	Tamilnadu (5.4)
2023	380012	U.P. (36.9)	Bihar (17.3)	West Bengal (7.5)	Rajasthan (6.4)	Tamilnadu (5.0)

Source: Computed by author from emigration clearance data of labour migration from India to Gulf countries. Accessed from [http://: www.emigrate.gov.in](http://www.emigrate.gov.in)

Data collection and analysis technique

It used a mixed method approach where qualitative information is followed by quantitative information in the procedure of collection of primary data. Qualitative data was collected by informal interview, focus group discussion (FGDs) and passive observation method while quantitative data was collected through a structured schedule under a cross-sectional study design and situation recall method. Qualitative data is analyzed by narrative, description and case studies while quantitative data is analyzed by descriptive statistics according to the requirement of the study. Therefore, both qualitative and quantitative study designs are followed for better justification of the study (Flow chart 1).

Figure 1: Research Design

Source: Figure 1, Taukeer 2020:127

4. Result and Discussion

Qualitative Aspect

There is well-developed culture of migration from North India to Gulf countries within well-developed cultural region of migration. In this study, it was found that it was not only a matter of international migration but also a matter of internal migration because migrant labourers migrated to Mumbai before migration to Gulf countries. This shows that internal migration led to international migration. It happens due to the wage differential between India and the Gulf. These consequences worked as “push and pull” factors of migration in the rural-based economy of India. These migrant labourers migrated to Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Qatar and other GCC states with hopes of a better life for their left behind family members at root and engaged as blue-collar workers in the bottom segmentation of the labour market in Gulf countries. These return migrant labourers said that they

were satisfied with the working conditions of Gulf countries and used to send huge remittances to their households. These consequences created a structural transformation in migrant households because the impact of Gulf migration improved the socio-economic status of migrant households. The consequences of the impact of Gulf migration created a form of demonstration culture of Gulf migration where the nexus of globalization and migration led the cultural migration but the impact of COVID-19 largely affected the migrants and created socio-economic and cultural contradictions discriminations and challenges. ⁱ

Quantitative Aspect

Socio-Economic Profile of Return Migrant Labourers

There was a crucial role of the demographic dividend in the function of migration where a vast majority of the return migrant labourers were in the age group between 18 and 35 years while the rest were in the age group between 36 and 60 years. In the context of the average age of return migrant labourers, it shows that the average age of return migrant labourers is 39.3 years in Kushinagar followed by 39.1 years in Siwan, 33.4 years in Maharajganj, 32.4 years in Jhunjhunu, 32.1 years in Gopalganj and 29.6 years in Churu. It can be analysed that these return migrant labourers were young due to the explicit impact of demographic dividend in India (Tables 6 & 7).

Table 6: Age Composition of Return Migrant Labourers (In per cent)

Age group	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushinagar	Maharajganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
18-25	1.6	12.4	3.6	24.8	37.2	30.0
26-35	36.0	58.6	34.4	41.6	44.4	34.0
36-45	40.0	21.1	40.0	29.2	12.8	28.0
46-60	22.4	7.9	22.0	4.4	5.6	8.0
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

ⁱ Information is based on informal interview, focus group discussion and passive observation method among return migrants and their family members in Uttar Pradesh from 2017 to 2018 and recent field works in North India in 2023.

Table 7: Average Age of Return Migrant Labourers

Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
Kushinagar	Maharajganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
39.3	33.4	39.1	32.1	29.6	32.4

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

The tendency of migration from North India to Gulf countries was led by Muslims due to the well-developed culture of migration among Muslims in rural North India (Table 8).

Table 8: Religious Composition of Return Migrant Labourers (In per cent)

Religion	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopal ganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Hindu	28.4	13.1	37.2	5.6	27.2	36.0
Muslims	71.6	86.9	62.0	94.4	72.4	62.0
Other	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.0	2.0
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

Out of the total return migrant labourers, cent per cent of the return migrant labourers were males due to the patriarchal based society and traditional Islamic-based culture in rural North India (Table 9).

Table 9: Gender Composition of Return Migrant Labourers (In per cent)

Gender composition	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Male	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Female	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

There was variation in the structure of skills of return migrant labourers comprising unskilled, semi-skilled, unskilled and highly skilled migrant workers due to the structure of the labour market in Gulf countries (Table 10).

Table 10: Marital Status of Return Migrant Labourers (In per cent)

Marital Status	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopalg anj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Married	76.0	83.3	84.0	69.6	58.4	58.0
Unmarried and Other (in a casual relationship, In a serious committed relationship, Widowed, Divorced/ Separate)	24.0	16.7	16.0	30.4	41.6	42.0
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

Out of the total return migrant labourers, there was variation in the educational qualification of the return migrant labourers; a vast majority of the return migrant labourers were educated below the secondary and up to higher secondary. Apart, the rest of the return migrant labourers did have vocational degrees, general education, professional graduate, postgraduate and doctorate. Therefore, it can be analyzed that there was a representation of less educated return migrant labourers in Gulf countries (Table 11).

Table 11: Multiple Response of Return Migrant Labourers about Educational Status (In per cent)

Education	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Mahara jganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhnujhunu
Below the Secondary	16.0	34.7	22.4	39.2	38.0	26.4
Up to higher Secondary	46.0	55.4	38.0	47.2	52.0	48.8
Vocational Degree	17.6	9.1	21.2	9.6	2.0	11.6
General Education	22.0	0.8	25.2	3.6	7.6	12.0
Professional Graduate	6.0	0.0	7.2	0.0	1.6	3.6
Post Graduation and Doctorate	2.8	0.0	3.6	0.8	0.0	5.2
Total	n=250	n=250	n=250	n=250	n=250	n=250

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

There was variation in the structure of skills of return migrant labourers comprising unskilled, semi-skilled, unskilled and highly skilled migrant workers due to the structure of the labour market in Gulf countries (Table 12).

Table 12: Skill Wise Composition of Return Migrant labourers (In Per cent)

Skills	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopal ganj	Churu	Jhunujhunu
Unskilled	17.2	77.7	13.2	12.4	80.0	45.2
Semi Skilled	17.2	12.3	17.6	28.0	5.0	26.0
Skilled	54.8	10.0	54.0	57.6	12.4	20.0
Highly Skilled (Like Dr. Engineer and Other), Businessman	10.8	0.0	15.2	2.0	2.6	8.8
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0(n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023-24

Out of the total return migrant labourers, return migrant labourers reported that migrant labourers worked as manual labourers, drivers, technicians, plumbers, masons and technicians. It can be analyzed that a vast majority of the return migrant labourers worked as blue-collar workers in the bottom segment of the labour market in Gulf countries (Table 13).

Table 13: Occupational Category of Return Migrant Labourers (In Per cent)

Occupation	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Labour	12.0	23.6	11.3	32.3	38.8	22.3
Driver	14.8	61.2	8.9	38.3	45.6	39.3
Technician	34.0	11.6	21.0	21.0	3.0	19.8
Other	39.2	3.6	58.8	8.4	12.6	18.6

(Plumber, Associate, Mason, Supervisor, Manager, Sales executive)						
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023-24

Process of Migration to Gulf Countries

There was a crucial role of internal migration in international migration because a vast majority of the return migrant labourers were involved in internal migration with the purpose of gaining skills of jobs and earnings before Gulf migration (Table 14).

Table 14: Response of Return migrant Labourers about Internal Migration before Gulf Migration (In Per cent)

Internal migration	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhnunjhunu
Yes	53.5	78.0	19.5	61.7	90.0	40.4
No	34.5	12.0	76.0	12.8	8.4	43.2
Prefer not to say	12.5	10.0	4.5	25.5	1.6	16.4
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

There was a crucial role of the push and pull factors of migration because migrant labourers migrated to Gulf countries due to availability of the better jobs with higher wages compared to low wages in India (Table 15).

Table 15: Multiple Response of Return Migrant Labourers about Reason of Migration to Gulf Countries (In per cent)

Reason of Migration	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopal ganj	Churu	Jhnuj hunu
Unemployment	13.2	56.8	34.5	20.4	47.6	21.7
To Earn and repay the debt	16.4	6.4	15.7	12.8	2.0	8.4
Shortage of Land	18.0	5.6	10.8	3.6	2.0	9.2
Dissatisfaction with previous job	13.6	6.8	9.6	6.8	6.0	15.3
Better employment opportunity	30.0	4.4	34.5	8.8	8.0	20.1
All of the above	39.6	21.2	30.9	52.8	40.0	48.2
Total	n =250	n =250	n =250	n =250	n =250	n =250

Source: field survey 2023-2024

Migrant labourers got information about jobs through kinship networks including relatives and friends. There was a crucial role in social media, news paper. MNCs, registered recruitment agents and manpower supplier. Therefore, both formal and informal channels played a crucial role in the function of migration (Table 16).

Table 16: Multiple Response of Return Migrant Labourers about Source of Information about Jobs in Gulf Countries (In per cent)

Source of information	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhnuj hunu
Social Media	1.6	55.6	7.2	26.1	42.8	22.1
News Paper	7.6	4.8	3.6	9.6	0.4	5.8
MNCs	2.8	6.0	1.6	4.8	0.0	7.9

Relatives	20.8	3.6	21.6	9.2	4.8	18.9
Friends	24.0	1.6	24.8	6.0	6.8	17.9
Manpower supplier	61.6	6.0	52.0	19.3	13.6	38.4
Registered recruitment agents	2.0	22.8	11.2	36.1	37.2	27.4
Total	n =250	n =250	n =250	n=250	n =250	n =190

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

There was variation in the financial cost of migration to Gulf countries because a vast majority of the return migrant labourers expended INR 15, 000 to INR 99,000 and rest of the return migrant labourers expended INR 100000 to INR 150000 (Table 17).

Table 17: Response of Return Migrant Labourers about Financial Cost of Travel of Migration (In Per cent)

Financial cost of travel of migration in INR	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharajganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Between 50 thousand to 99 thousand	68.7	57.4	56.2	44.9	88.4	63.6
Between 15 thousand to 49 thousand	16.5	7.1	27.0	9.7	7.6	16.8
Between one lakh to one lakh forty thousand	11.6	9.2	10.5	13.4	3.0	5.0
Up to one lakh fifty thousand	0.0	26.3	0.4	25.5	0.5	11.2
Free of cost	3.2	0.0	5.9	6.5	0.5	3.4
Total	100 (n=250)	100 (n=250)	100(n =250)	100 (n=250)	100(n=250)	100 (n=250)

Source: Field Survey 2023-2024.

Migrant labourers arranged the financial needs of migration, through informal mode but a few return migrant labourers reported that they arranged the financial needs of migration through bank loan. Therefore, it can be analyzed that there was a crucial role of the formal and informal modes in the process of arrangement of financial needs of migration to Gulf countries (Table 18).

Table 18: Multiple Responses of Return Migrant Labourers about Arrangement Financial Needs of Migration to Gulf Countries (In Per cent)

Source of financial needs for migration to Gulf	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhunjh unu
Sold Property	7.2	52.2	13.6	26.4	42.4	17.6
Money Lander	28.0	11.2	32.2	12.6	5.2	5.6
Personal Loan	18.8	7.2	3.7	14.2	4.0	13.2
Bank Loan	8.0	4.0	1.7	3.7	1.6	6.0
Family members/Friends.	40.8	23.5	39.3	42.3	45.2	56.4
Through self savings	37.2	4.8	30.6	10.2	7.2	24.4
Not applicable	1.2	0.0	3.7	3.3	0.8	2.4
Total	100 (n=250)	=250)				

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia was the largest destination for migrant labourers followed by the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Oman, Kuwait and Bahrain (Table 19).

Table 19: Destination Country of Return Migrant Labourers in Gulf Countries (In Per cent)

Destination	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhunjh unu
Bahrain	5.2	36.4	10.2	26.8	0.8	8.4
Sultanate of Oman	10.0	11.2	9.4	10.6	8.8	10.4

Kuwait	8.4	8.0	13.5	7.5	13.6	17.3
United Arab Emirates	22.0	8.0	19.0	10.6	19.2	17.3
Qatar	15.6	7.2	12.0	7.5	8.8	12.9
Kingdom of Saudi Arabia	38.4	29.2	35.9	37.0	48.8	33.7
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

Out of the total return migrant labourers, a vast majority of the return migrant labourers earned INR 20000 to INR 70000 per month and the rest of the return migrant labourers earned above INR 71000 per month (Table 20).

Table 20: Per Month Income of Return Migrant Labourers in Gulf countries in INR (In per cent)

Per Month in INR	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushinagar	Maharajganj	Siwan	Goaplganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
20000-30000	0.8	38.4	6.0	35.3	40.0	34.0
31000-40000	12.8	41.6	23.2	22.9	42.0	30.0
41000-50000	36.0	10.0	31.2	21.3	9.2	13.6
51000-70000	35.6	6.0	22.8	15.3	6.0	12.0
71000 and above	14.8	0.0	14.4	5.0	2.8	8.8
Prefer not to say	0.0	4.0	2.4	0.2	0.0	1.6
Total	100 (n=250)	100 (n=250)	100 (n=250)	100 (n=250)	100 (n=250)	100 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

The average per month income was INR 54790 per migrant labourer in Kushinagar followed by INR 44264 in Siwan, INR 39835 in Gopalganj, INR 35010 in Churu, INR 33935 in Maharajganj and INR 32613 in Jhunjhunu. There is variation in the average monthly income of migrant labourers according to their skills in jobs and the structure of the labour market in Gulf countries (Table 21).

Table 21: Comparative Figure of Average Monthly Income of Return Migrant Labourers in INR

Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
Kushinagar	Maharajganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
54790	33935	44264	39835	35010	32613

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

Migrant labourers lived in labour apartments provided by their sponsors in Gulf countries because these migrant labourers worked as contract labourers under the *Kafala* (sponsorship) system in Gulf countries (Table 22).

Table 22: Response of Return Migrant Labourers about Accommodation Facilities in Gulf Countries (In Per cent)

Response of migrant labourers	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Goopal ganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Yes	85.4	99.6	89.7	95.9	96.0	83.1
No	14.6	0.4	10.3	4.1	4.0	16.9
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=2500)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

Out of the total return migrant labourers, a vast majority of the return migrant labourers reported that working conditions were excellent and good while the rest of the return migrant labourers reported that working conditions were average and bad based on their perception of working conditions in the Gulf countries (Table 23).

Table 23: Response of Return Migrant Labourers about Working Conditions in Gulf Countries (In per cent)

Response of migrant labourers	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Goapl ganj	Churu	Rajasthan
Excellent	57.3	10.4	43.6	13.7	10.4	28.1
Good	30.2	77.3	34.4	67.3	85.6	42.2
Average	11.7	10.4	20.0	12.1	4.0	20.9
Bad	0.8	1.9	2.0	6.9	0.0	8.8
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

There was a large impact of COVID-19 on return migrant labourers during their stay in Gulf countries because these migrant labourers returned to India in an uncertain way (Table 24).

Table 24: Response of Return Migrant Labourers about Impact of COVID-19 during their Stay in Gulf Countries (In per cent)

Response of migrant laboureres	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopal ganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Yes	78.0	65.9	83.7	43.2	62.0	35.1
No	16.4	32.9	11.0	52.5	37.2	60.9
Maybe	5.6	1.2	5.3	4.3	0.8	4.0
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=249)	100.0 (n=245)	100.0 (n=236)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=248)

Source: Field survey 2023-2024

Return migrant labourers reported that they got medical allowances in Gulf countries because they worked as contract guest labourers in Gulf countries (Table 25).

Table 25: Response of Return Migrant Labourers about Medical Allowances in Gulf Countries (In per cent)

Response of migrant labourers	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopal ganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Yes	73.9	82.4	65.8	81.2	98.0	89.9
No	14.9	17.6	20.6	15.8	2.0	6.0
Maybe	11.2	0.0	13.6	3.0	0.0	4.1
Total	100.0 (n=249)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=243)	100.0 (n=234)	100.0 (n=248)	100.0 (n=248)

Source: Field survey 2023-2024

Impact of Gulf Migration

There were different sources of inflow of remittances from Gulf countries to India where Bank and money transfer exchanges were major sources of inflow of remittances. Therefore, it can be analyzed that migrant labourers used to send remittances through proper channels compared to informal mode (Table 26).

Table 26: Multiple Responses of Return Migrant Labourers about Mode of Inflow of Remittances to Homelands (In per cent)

Mode	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushinagar	Maharajganj	Siwan	Gopalganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Through Agent	3.6	1.2	0.8	1.7	1.6	4.4
Through Friend	14.1	1.2	5.7	1.3	2.0	10.1
Through Bank	81.9	97.2	91.8	99.2	95.2	87.5
Through Money Transfer Exchange (Western Union, Telitransfer)	20.9	2.4	26.5	4.2	4.4	14.1

Total	n=250	n =250	n =250	n=250	n=250	n=250
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Source: Field survey 2023- 2024

Migrant households invested a vast proportion of the remittances in unproductive items (households, building homes, marriage, and home renovation compared to productive items (education and investment). It can be analyzed that the investment pattern led to the demonstration impact of Gulf migration in rural North India (Table 27).

Table 27: Multiple Response about Utilization Pattern of Remittances in Migrant Households (in per cent)

Utilization Pattern of Remittances	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopal ganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Households	52.2	3.8	73.9	9.0	20.6	28.3
Building Home	33.2	1.4	37.6	6.8	9.4	23.9
Marriage	29.3	0.5	23.7	4.0	7.5	20.1
Home Renovation	28.5	1.0	29.8	6.8	16.9	24.5
On Education	36.5	1.4	47.8	9.0	15.0	21.7
All of the above	24.9	96.2	20.0	84.7	71.9	58.7
Investment	2.4	0.0	5.3	5.6	1.3	7.6
Total	n=250	n=250	n=250	n=250	n=250	n=250

Source: Field survey 2023- 2024

There was a significant impact of Gulf migration due to enhancing social status, improvement in living standards, and improvement in children's education. Therefore, it can be analyzed that Gulf migration improved the socio-economic development of family members of migrant households (Table 28).

Table 28: Multiple Response of Return Migrant Labourers about Impact of Migration on Migrant's Family (In per cent)

Social Status	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopal ganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Enhanced social status	14.2	0.4	14.1	2.8	2.8	4.0
Improved standard of living due to remittances	17.4	0.8	25.0	2.4	2.8	6.9
Children education improved	4.5	0.8	5.6	2.8	2.0	2.8
All of the above	80.2	98.8	75.0	99.6	95.6	93.5
Total	n=247	n=250	n=248	n=246	n=249	n=248

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

Out of the total return migrant households, a vast majority of the migrant households found themselves “much better than earlier” and “better” conditions compared to the rest return migrant households reported their socio-economic status as having no change, bad and worse than earlier. Therefore, it can be analyzed that there was both positive and negative impact of Gulf migration on migrant households in rural North India (Table 29).

Table 29: Response of Return Migrant Labourers about change in Socio-Economic Status of Migrant Households (In per cent)

Response of Migrant Labourers	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopal ganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
Much better than earlier	43.0	33.6	57.5	59.2	45.6	67.6
Better	40.2	29.2	32.8	31.8	10.4	15.4
No Change	11.6	1.0	9.7	4.0	2.0	6.5

Bad	4.2	32.4	0.0	2.0	40.0	10.5
Worst than earlier	1.0	3.8	0.0	3.0	2.0	0.0
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=250)

Source: Field survey 2023- 2024

Women of migrant households used to take the role of head of the households in the absence of migrants in Gulf countries. These consequences can be analyzed that it enhanced women's empowerment in migrant households (Table 30).

Table 30: Response of Migrant Labourers about Migrant's Wife taken the Role of Head of the Household in the absence of Migrant (In per cent)

Response of migrant labourers	Uttar Pradesh		Bihar		Rajasthan	
	Kushi nagar	Maharaj ganj	Siwan	Gopal ganj	Churu	Jhunjhunu
No	14.4	72.1	13.0	49.1	67.1	23.5
Not sure	19.2	0.5	9.0	4.2	3.8	15.0
Yes	66.4	27.4	78.0	46.7	29.1	61.5
Total	100.0 (n=250)	100.0 (n=208)	100.0 (n=234)	100.0 (n=169)	100.0 (n=158)	100.0 (n=153)

Source: Field survey 2023 -2024

Based on the above concise analysis of the result part, it can be concluded that both economic and non-economic factors determined the function of migration from North India to Gulf countries in the context of globalization of migration in rural North India. These consequences developed a form of the cultural region of migration as well as migration-based communities. These consequences also led to the huge inflow of remittances in migrant households and the investment pattern of remittances enhanced the socio-economic status of migrant households. These perspectives were reflected in the socio-economic and cultural behaviour of return migrants and their family members positively.

Apart, the impact of COVID-19 largely influenced the migrant labourers because they lost their jobs in Gulf countries and returned to root in distress way. In fact, migration from the Gulf region is in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations. It contributes to the alleviation of poverty, the improvement of access to education and the enhancement of social mobility. Nevertheless, the interruptions that were caused by the COVID-19 pandemic have shown that there is a need for migration frameworks that are particularly more secure and sustainable. To safeguard beneficial impacts of migration, it is essential to establish support structures that can minimize the devastating effects of crises of COVID kind.

Conclusion

The phenomenon of Gulf migration from North India is multidimensional. It is propelled by economic and social factors under the broader structure of globalization. The migration from rural North India to Gulf nations has profoundly influenced the economic and social situations of those regions. The influx of remittances from migrant workers has improved the financial stability of families. It has resulted in the progress of education, housing and general living conditions. The socio-economic progress has generated a cultural manifestational effect due to the Gulf migration. However, it is also found that the COVID-19 pandemic has revealed vulnerabilities within this migration system. A significant number of migrant workers faced unemployment and returned home under severe conditions. This highlights the need of establishing better procedures to safeguard migrant workers and to guarantee the long-term viability of their contributions to the growth of the nation at large. The consequences of these occurrences brought to light the fragile balance that exists between migration as an economic need and the dangers that are linked with exogenous shocks related to health and stability.

This research confirms that Gulf migration has substantially aided socio-economic progress in rural North India. Nonetheless, it is contended that specific crises emerge from issues pertaining to worker exploitation, inadequate social safeguards and the ramifications of global crises such as COVID-19. All factors need the re-evaluation of certain policies and the establishment of legislation for the protection of migrant workers. The construction of sustainable pathways is essential to protect the

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welfare of migrants and their families throughout critical periods and ensure that migrant workers encounter minimal obstacles and dangers. The remittances they send are exempt from taxes, obligations, and interest. We may use them at our discretion. We are not required to seek assistance and guidance from external entities such as the IMF and World Bank. Otherwise, when we get a loan from any entity, we are compelled to adhere to their guidance about where and how to invest.

Further, it can be also concluded that the matter of migration was positively associated with the agenda of sustainable development goals (SDGs) of the United Nations because the impact of Gulf migration was being reflected as sustainable migration but the impact of COVID-19 worked as the hurdle in the way of sustainable migration. Therefore, it can be recommended that there is a need to set up a mechanism to ensure the sustainable impact of migration in migrant households in rural north India under the United Nations and the government of India.

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